

Role of Intramuscularly Administrable Vaccines in Secretary Antibody's Production Mechanisms

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1. INTRODUCTION

In accordance with our biochemistry-based philosophy and the objectives of this work, here are four concepts with which the interested readers should first familiarize themselves: a disease is an abnormal metabolism that can influence on intact metabolic processes; under the word “disease”, we will focus on communicable (infectious) diseases; when we talk about infection, we mean a metabolism disorder caused by the invasion of a pathogen; and among these pathogens, SARS-CoV-2, which we encountered 20 years ago as SARS-CoV, is the cause of the century's pandemic - a pandemic from which the Globe should take a lesson (at least after unnecessarily crumbled 7 million lives), if we want such disasters will be the first and the last! Unless...

1.1 Background of this research project

1.1.1 Since, the first months of the pandemic, we tried to alert what measures better to take

As soon as the COVID-19 obtained a pandemic status, until our lab closed due to quarantine, we were engaged in a laboratory based two researching activities: identifying whether Banknotes can play a fomite role in Corona transmission incidents and identifying the maximum temperature of hot water that human hand can resist (inserting hands into hot water for not less than three minutes) - as an alternative to sanitizing measure in mass gatherings [1]).

However, after the experimental laboratory shut down, we switched into field and clinical case survey-study: Beginning from March, 2020, using our background understandings to the virus, we tried alerting public, together with started criticizing-commenting on WHO's guiltless/deliberated unscientific recommendations, such as: its 20 seconds singing the “happy birth day” clip to determine the durability of hand washing; moreover, about unjustified statement as if SARS-CoV-2 may not be airborne-aerosol type of pathogen; and against WHO's and CDC disputes on one-two meters distance must be kept for not to be infected (according to our mathematic-physics based calculation, the virus in a weak wind can even move a kilometer distance to infect [1]). Anyway, against media based disinformation, as seen in figure 1, we too tried to elaborate out our suggestions through social media and even by email.

Figure 1: Since March, 2020, first our several alerts on the pandemic issues to the world through twitter March 28 we posted: *Politicians shouldn't interfere in COVID-19 taskforce's activities and March 31, 2020, emailed to UN and WHO a suggestion about how to create effective task forces on COVID-19, including any catastrophe (in general). April 30 we wrote that remdesivir may NOT stop the pandemic and April 31 we replied that talking about sunlight's impact on Corona is not a novel, since every membrane's protein easily can be denaturalized by heat!*

1.1.2 Our publications on the COVID-19 issues and responses

Next, in July and September 2020, we published the first two awareness articles [1,2]. Since then, with the aim of dispatching our findings as quickly as possible to concerned organizations and the public, we have published 7 articles in three types of journals with quick publishing trends. Among them, in the work published in December 2021 [3,4], we highlighted main doubts about the effectiveness of immunization through intramuscularly administered vaccine (IMAV) to stop not only SARS-CoV-2, but also others HROS pathogens as follows: Responsible and regulatory agencies within a country and internationally (at large) engage in aggressive advertising for these unnecessary IMAVs (in our latest 8th article on COVID-19: Correlation between the exceptional nature of the system of human respiratory organs and...”) – such our postulation of 2021, ought to ignite raising “doubts” about others known vaccines too, such as vaccines against influenza-tuberculosis, etc.

Nonetheless, the conclusions on these doubts about the effectiveness of IMAV against Corona, including on their boosters' drawbacks, in 2022 at the international conference, we have delivered an elaborated speech [5].

However, we felt that even republishing in a journal [6] for the second time, did not give the desired result. That was why we planned to present it again in August and November 2023. Refer to figure 2. However, even though, our abstracts were passed review processes, due to lack of money for registration to the conferences, we were unable to provide the presenting! Anyways, either, these journals (where we published) are not popular or because our researches' contents were not desirables for Big-Pharma's business, no one paid attention to such works - works that were capable of not only minimizing the destructive role of the pandemic, but also have ability to direct the health sciences' society to think about the alteration of Global medicinal practices at least in the field of HROS pathogens and vaccination principles!

Figure 2: Two accepted works to be presented in international conferences

2A: accepted the whole work “Feasibility of IMAVs against HROS Tracts’ Pathogens” for August 17-19, 2023 and
 2B: accepted the sub-article - “Role of Intramuscularly/subcutaneously Administrable Mode of Vaccination in the SIgA’s production Mechanism” for November 10-12, 2023

1.2 statement of the problem

Problems that forced us to launch this study are sorted into five sections:

1.2.1 Our warnings about the non-effectiveness of IMAVs against HROS pathogens have less impact
 As stated above in 1.1.2, especially the last two papers [4,6] didn’t receive enough attention and even we could not present them in international conferences.

On the other hand, those who have political-financial interests in this mode of vaccination have the possibility of dirtying journals and the media! as if the IMAV vaccination mode was the only feasible alternative to stop the COVID-19 pandemic. Without identifying: what type of vaccine; how it acts; and against which pathogen it is effective, they simply were manipulating-speculating on the two words: “vaccine” and “effective”! Certainly, it becomes sad and painful to see how the aggressive and anti-science business (it reminds us the alchemists’ era) is thriving within sphere of medicines!

Through social media and in some publishers too, to pretend as if vaccines are angels, they write “vaccine”: is safe-effective; protect from infection; decreases severity; even they do not hesitate to say that IMAV’s modes against Corona save lives”; etc. Furthermore, not only we asked the WHO the CDC to stop their dreadful actions, but even we requested the European Ombudsman and the Nobel Prize Committee (table 1), incase if they have the power to stop this kind of propaganda machines, which everywhere destructively advertising against humanity and science. Whether, innocently/deliberately, for us as a biochemist, this is uncontrollable century’s worst crime – offensive ads that were endorsed by authorities (refer to figure 3A,B). What additionally horrible is that the vaccines were mandatory!

@DessalegnTL · Oct 18, 2021
 Fauci: Americans who are fully vaccinated can enjoy the holiday season with their family
news.yahoo.com/fauci-american...
 via @Yahoo If you want a game change information, Pls, read the conclusion and part of an article "Uncertainties on vaccines' feasibility..." then will offer new work

from yahoo.com

A

Please, the recent vaccines are not feasible reposted

Dr. Tom Frieden ✓ ...

@DrTomFrieden · Jan 29, 2022

Replying to @DrTomFrieden

10 billion doses of lifesaving vaccines have been administered globally in just over a year. That's a stunning achievement, although vaccine inequity continues to cost lives and create the conditions for wily variants such as Omicron to emerge. What's wrong with this picture? 7/

B

Please, the recent vaccines are not feasible @Dessal... · Nov 16, 2020 ...
 Moderna says its vaccine is 94.5% effective in preventing COVID-19
news.yahoo.com/moderna-says-v... via @YahooNews Refer to my March 29, 20
 tweet: Impossible to have effective vaccine for such virus! Rather "stay at home" and "Masking Face" are the 2 prevention measures that can stop it!

C

Figure 3: Extra samples of stakeholders' aggressive advert for COVID-19 vaccines

On November 16, 2020 (fig 3C), to argue Moderna's 94% effectiveness, we posted that "Impossible to have effective vaccine for such virus ...within a short of time..." and as seen in figure 3A, on October 18, 2021, we offered to A. Fauci to pass through our article [7], where, in February 2021, we doubted about the feasibility of these vaccines

1.2.2 The simplest and cheapest measures against HROS pathogens vs. Big-pharma and pseudoscientists' vaccination options

Although, most with medicinal background should understand that the feasible option to stop any pathogen is - not to let it come into contact with its preferred living systems' site (for example, in most of HROS based infections, the easiest and effective prophylaxis measure is – not to let the pathogen having contact with oral and nostrils cavities [6]) and despite our efforts to alert the world, especially the responsible and regulatory stakeholders, about the non-feasibility of IMAV against HROS-based pathogens, this mode of vaccination, is still considered as the main option to eliminate the pandemic,

We are afraid that if not they themselves are going to involve in developing a factor-cause for another pandemic, the business oriented scientists at least will be ignorant to others effective prophylaxis measures. Certainly, together with business oriented pseudo-scientists (if he is a medical specialist, he even disobeys the Hippocrates Oath - "don't harm"), the pharm-industries, media, and even politicians, are doing their own profits-benefits. Unfortunately, we are afraid that for this prolonged and destructive pandemic, they may not become accountable! More, what we think awful is that in the near future, even the WHO (UN agency for Global health issues [2]) may not take the responsibility not only for what itself was misinforming, but also for its ignorance of different science based alerts (refer to figure 1 and table 1)! If that so, in the near future they could lead us to another worsen pandemic-catastrophe [2].

To/with whom was the deal	Way of interaction and the main content of the deal	Date of the deal
WHO	Emailed 4 main issues: such vaccine for this virus is useless, awareness making about the virus, stop saying "not airborne" and stop saying "1 meter distancing is enough" is airborne-air	3/28/2020 and 4/3/2020

	droplet, and taskforce but not politicians should comment	
Nobel	Do not nominate the mRNA developer?	9/10/2022
FDA, CDC, and media	We wrote enormous letter to them about prophylaxis, but not vaccine is feasible to stop the pandemic	2020-2022
EU Parliament	Website the FDA, CDC,EMA, WHO do not want to consider our findings that IMAV vaccines are useless against Corona	2022
EU, ombudsman	EMA and WHO do not respond to our question about the feasibility of vaccines against covid	02/11/2022 4:27PM
EMA agency	Email and web based confirmation of EMA to our question about the useless of COVID vaccine	02/11/2022
Nobel	FB: Let the Nobel Committee investigate the vaccination issue	July 2023
Media	The New Times, BBC, Aljezira, CNN, Fox News, etc	Since 2020

1.2.3 being jobless after Ethiopian authorities banned our anti-IMAV research results

Surprisingly, either: his jealousy; due to our Amhara ethnicity; because of his dependency on politicians; or because someone offered him an advantage if he not let us revealing the messes of the business oriented mass vaccination, the president of our university, not only banned us from presenting to the academic staff the results of the study against the IMAV of COVID- 19, but even apparently in revenge (we accused him of his anti-academic freedom), first ignored our possible academic promotion, terminated for a month from work, and now we are jobless at all! Additionally, although the Ethiopian Ministry of Innovation and Technology requested Gondor and Addis Ababa Colleges of Health Sciences to evaluate our findings, they also refused to do so (Figure 4) . This is why, due to depression and income problems, we have halted all research activities and from blaming vaccine developers. Instead, we begin looking for means of subsistence.

Figure 4: Ethiopian MiNT request health science colleges to evaluate our research findings

The content of the above Ethiopian MiNT letter can be expressed in English as follows: Date March 21/2022; Subject:- Requesting to evaluate research results; Text body – Dr. dessalegn Temesgen claims that the recent mode of vaccinations is not feasible to stop Corona and others respiratory tracts' based pathogens. Therefore, we kindly request your health college to evaluate his works and give us your feedback

1.2.4 Even our posts do not receive valuable concerns

After realizing that not only we couldn't present research results even in our native country!, but also since, our publications against this mode of prophylactic measures (using IMAV against Corona) were paying no attention. From the end of 2021 (after publishing our work [3]), we openly oppose IMAV, via social networks! Even the profile photo of one of our Facebook pages has changed (Facebook profile and X are named - Please, the vaccine does not work (refer to figure 5). In it, one can read – “The worst Century's advert against humanity and science is that of RTV”. to show the vitality of masks [4,6], all of our portraits, including our email's profile, come with face masks (because, we attached a masked photo!, there was one situation where a conference organizer refused to accept our abstract.

Figure 5: To show the vitality of face mask, profiles of social pages changed with masked photo

We are not alone to be worried on such messes: although, their arguments are based on only statistical data (lack of science based justifications, because of which business oriented media and even some scientists are trying demoralizing them), there are not few anti-vaccination groups. Undoubtedly, due to lack of awareness that it is airborne, they (anti-vaxx) are saying “my body is mine”, with which we are not agree. And more importantly, on how SARS-CoV-2 infects, in the form of a petition, 31 high ranked scientists in an article [8], well expressed their concern as follows: “the struggle of a large group of experts who came together at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic to warn the world about the risk of airborne transmission...”. Furthermore, these authors, at least indirectly confirm our

post of March 28, 2020 (refer to figure 1 and [2]), mainly among their 4 points, the first two: Multidisciplinary mechanisms should be created by which decision-makers should be accountable for using or rejecting science, in a transparent and timely manner and decision makers should use the best available science and not confront the science in order to fit a decision that may hinge on multiple factors...”.

Although, these authors didn't reply to our invitation to have contact-discussion, their phrases elicited us to prepare the two years intensive study's result with a title - “Feasibility of IMAVs against HROS Tracts' Pathogens” on COVID-19 issues. Unfortunately, due to its huge size, publishers recommended us to partition the material into three sub-articles. Because of which, we split it into three sub-articles: Role of Intramuscularly Administrable Vaccines in Secretary immunoglobulin A Antibody's (SIgA) Production Mechanisms; Exceptionalities in Human Respiratory System's Anatomy-physiology and its Pathogens; and determining the Vaccination's Feasibility. However, as seen in figure 5, although a publisher accepted the first sub-article for publication, we couldn't afford a \$55 fee for each of three sub-articles!

Dtl Leye

@LeyeDtl · Jun 19, 2023

Dear all, now the vaccination issue, because of which I lost every thing: sister, promotion and even job, is going to be clear!

According to our 7+1 PUBLISHED WORKS, THE INTRAMUSCULARLY ADMINISTRABLE VACCINES ARE USELESS TO STOP RESPIRATORY TRACTS' BASED PATHOGENS!
with respect

A

[https://figshare.com › articles...](https://figshare.com/articles...)

Role of Intramuscularly Administrable Vaccine in Secretary Antibody's Production Mechanism - Figshare

Nov 17, 2023 – Role of Intramuscularly Administrable Vaccines in Secretary Antibody's

B

C

Comments

Top Newest

and to follow our Community Guidelines

@dtlleye3036 · 6 mo ago

Let us see whether these laurates will pronounce the century's anti humanity and anti science advert – mRNA CoVID-19 vaxxs are effective"

Like Comment Reply

Add a comment...

D

Figure 6: Acceptance sub article about SIgA production and posts in social media, since July 2023 After warning the vaccine producers, first on June 19, 2023 we posted that the IMAVs are useless to stop respiratory based pathogens, including Corona (fig 6A). As seen in fig 6B, Nov 17, 2023 the Figshare deposited our sub-article “Role of IMAV in SIgA Production Mechanism”, in fig 6C shown the its acceptance by a journal. And in fig 6D, during the start of Nobel Lecture on Physiology or Medicine, we posted online “Let us see whether these laurates confirm the effectiveness of IMAVs. However, they genuinely finished their lectures without advertng for these useless vaccines!

1.2.5 Dangerous trend for the next possible pandemic

Certainly, today, even if, without any recognition of the anti-science misdeeds that took place during the three years of the COVID-19 era, doubts-disputes appear if not regarding to recent COVID-19 vaccines efficacy, at least their safety issues. Within these last two years (2023 and 2024) Information about vaccination based injuries are escalating intensively. Most of those who raise vaccine's safety issues are accusing politicians and vaccine developers. To the contrary, for such global damage, we do not blame the vaccine developers (for us, they are simply tax-paying businessmen), but rather the pseudo-scientists; politicians-authorities; responsible international bodies, in particular the WHO; and the media are the main engines of anti-scientific propaganda. They said as if mRNA based IMAVs protect against reinfection and infection of others! As seen in figure 2 and 5, we tried openly argued their posts!

What more worried us was that, although in 2022 we tried to alert the Nobel Prize Committee (refer to table 1 and figure 5C) not to recognize any work related to the developing of COVID-19 vaccines, during their announcement of winners in Physiology or medicine in 2023, the president and others members of the committee tried to reflect positive attitudes to these vaccines.

To the contrary, although, we are not sure that whether they took into account our recommendation (we tried to address them through media and email) - not to confirm the so called mRNA based COVID-19 vaccines' effectiveness during their public lectures, both the Nobel Laureates in Physiology or Medicine of 2023 didn't say anything (figure 6D) about the COVID-19 vaccines' efficacy. Further, the Australian Royal pandemic Committee enquired us to offer suggestions on the nature of COVID-19 and its vaccines' safety; although with only statistical data (analysis based on numbers), which lack scientific justifications (proofing), after many informal articles published (posted) on the safety issues problem of COVID-19 vaccines; and after the world watched Anthony Fauci's testimony (our messages to him and the CDC (refer to figure 7C,B,A) about these useless vaccines), we resumed looking for a journal that can accept with total waiver of publication costs for our three sub-articles - articles that together can firmly put to end the speculations about the "effectiveness" and "safety" issues of IMAVs against pathogens including Corona.

@DessalegnTL · Oct 7, 2020
 'It is a slaughter': Infectious disease icon asks CDC director to expose White House, orchestrate his own firing news.yahoo.com/slaughter-info... via @YahooNews Face mask is advantageous, where as vaccine for such type of virus and for this time frame is somewhat a fantasy.

Figure 7: Extra attempts to address our concerns to CDC responsible bodies through social posts Restlessly, tried to inform CDC leaders about the none feasibility of the vaccines: as seen in fig 7A, on Oct 21, 2020, replied to A. fauci's that he should trust the public's desire, but not politicians. To the Chief of CDC too (fig 7B) replied that being vaccinated can NOT help not to be infected or from infecting others. In 6D, on Oct. 7, 2020, we expressed that Facemask is preferable, whereas trying to develop such vaccines and within this time frame is somewhat a fantasy!

1.3 Hypotheses

To what extent can the vaccination mode of IMAVs be feasible to stop HROS pathway-dependent pathogens?

As indicated in 1.2.4 and 1.2.5, we become confident that IMAVs do not stop HROS-based pathogens! Therefore, for our hypothesis based question mentioned above, in advance, the answer with 80% confidence is 'NO, they can't!'

1.4 objectives of the research

1.4.1 General objective:

Analyzing, relevant literature based data: before COVID-19; during this pandemic era; and meta-analysis vs. our publications with biochemistry context on how to combat HROS based pathogens

1.4.2 Specific objectives on the Role of IMAVs in SIgA production mechanisms

Identifying the biology-nature of SIgA

Analyzing the role of IMAVs' mode of vaccination in SIgA formation processes

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY-DESIGN

Although, it was better to set on clinical lab test part, as we have expressed it in the work [3] of its methodology section, due to lack of permission and budget from our university to conduct medical based experiment, instead, we used the metadata (aiming to compensate lack of lab research) in this mixed research design [9-11]

2.1 To achieve the mentioned objectives, this research design is going to rely on the comparing-analyzing-evaluating the data of 5 sorts (variables): literature on vaccination-pathogen issues, which was documented (fixed) before the pandemic (mainly must include books written before the 2019); our previous works; today's (pandemic era) researchers' publications on the issue; and of course the metadata analysis-synthesis [11], (we hope, to a certain extent it can compensate our deficits in experimental works!

2.2 In general, for the literature-based data collection, we initially had 30 questions, for which, we planned to get answers. However, at the middle of the data collection task, we reduced the questions into 20 main working questions. Next, after gathering the whole data for the work, we fused them into half (10 data types that together can capable to answer the hypothesis) categories as follows:

2.2.1 Anatomy....

2.2.2 Exceptionality...;

2.2.3 Nature of HROS based pathogens, such as SARS-CoV-2, Flu, TB, Pneumonia, etc.

2.2.4 Immune systems and Principle of Vaccination

2.2.5 Nature of the antibody SIgA and its role against HROS based pathogens;

2.2.6 Why smallpox....?;

2.2.7 Role of face mask against ...

2.2.8 Pie chart of proportional measures ...

2.2.9 To a pathogenic context, what are the differences between ...

2.2.10 Can IMAV be feasible...?

Yes, we have analyzed these ten types of collected data and the sum of them helped us to post the first conclusion that the IMAV are useless to contain Corona and others HROS pathogens (refer figure 6A). Further, after awaiting any response from vaccine developers and relevant specialists, we tried to publish an article **“The Feasibility of Intramuscularly Administrable Mode of Vaccines against Pathogens of Human Respiratory Tracts”**. However, since, the article was huge in size (45+10 pages), the journals' editors recommended us to split it into three sub-articles.

Therefore, we clustered the above the ten divisions into 6 groups of tools that can capable to be used as scientific justifications to confirm the none feasibility of IMAVs against HROS based pathogens. However, to have three articles, we assembled them into three to prepare three sub-articles: 2.2.1+2.2.2; 2.2.3+2.2.4+2.2.5; and 2.2.6-2.2.10.

Hence, for this work – “Role of IMAVs in SIgA Production Mechanisms”, we are going to elaborate the results (literature data collected under 2.2.3 Nature of HROS based pathogens, such as SARS-CoV-2, Flu, TB, Pneumonia, etc.+ 2.2.4 Immune systems and Principle of Vaccination + 2.2.5 Nature of the antibody SIgA and its role against HROS based pathogens; here under:

3. RESULT

Here are materials (results in their short form): what we have gathered, compared, analyzed, and summarized-justified within these last two years (part of the prepared material for PPT based presentation during scientific conferences). However, due to the huge material (more than 45 pages) of this research project under a research title “The Feasibility of Intramuscularly Administrable Mode of Vaccines against Human Respiratory Tracts' Pathogens”, publishers refused to publish it. Therefore, we have decided to publish it by splitting into 3 articles. As indicated below, for this particular article,

we are going to elaborate the 2.2.3; 2.2.4 and 2.2.5 (refer to section 2.2 above) in the form of section 3.1; 3.2; and 3.3. However, for those, who are advanced, can go directly to sub-section 3.3:

3.1 Nature of HROS pathogens in general

General nature of HROS tracts based pathogens, such as Corona, Flu, TB, Pneumonia, etc. Although chronic-abnormality and infectious disease of HROS are in general expressed in many books and research articles, our concern is – HROS’s pathogens based infectious disease.

Except our works [4,6,7], in open access journals about SARS-CoV-2, sufficiently explored by different authors: among hundreds (if not thousands) works are easily available. From all of such works, we can synthesize: Almost all of HROS pathogens enter into the HROS through oral and nostril cavities; they are easily evolved; and directly/indirectly the works [12,13,18-24] show us that comparatively, the HROS’ pathogens are not systemic infection (to our interpretation, better relate the systemic to circulation based diseases) rather they trigger inflammation-cytokine storming causes to other organs too, about which we have mentioned in [6])

3.3 General nature of HROS tracts based pathogens, such as Corona, Flu, TB, Pneumonia, etc.

Although chronic-abnormality and infectious disease of HROS are in general expressed in many books and research articles, our concern is – HROS’s pathogens based infectious disease

1.3.1 Nature of HROS pathogens in general

Except our

circulation based diseases) rather they trigger inflammation-cytokine storming impacts to other organs too (we have mentioned in [6,8])

3.3.1.1 Life chain of HROS based pathogens

According

HROS – contact with epithelium-reproducing their-cavities-air). For more imagination, refer to figure 4 below.

3.3.1.2 Improper interpretation of pathogens’ nature

If we agree

instead of only hand washing, we{{ should have to cover mouth-nose or being at safe place.

Figure 8: general concept of HROS pathogens' infectious

However, stakeholders' negligence (may be until the vaccines are fully approved!) leads the globe to the

3.3.2 Bio-preconditions for HROS pathogens affect

Except infectious paths and host-epithelial cells (as seen in figure 4 either in atmosphere or within HROS), these

withstand such high temperature (refer to figure 5b).

Because: as

their hands are adopted to a high temperature) because in the work [25,26].

Therefore, probably, we can use hot water together or instead of sanitizer (except for surgeries, not

How much heat can withstand African hands?

Figure 9 (a,b): The possible high temperature based Corona's destruction (modified from [1])

3.3.3 Are HROS based pathogens systemic?

Based on 3.2

confuse with skin test for TB infection history).

3.3.4 Bio-stability of HROS pathogens

Additionally, the genetic based non stability issues is the most negative factor against achieving a success season new strains!

3.3.5 Summary of justifications on HROS pathogens in general:

Most (if not all)

spiking, but also cannot survive there against high constant temperature, enzymes, and others active metabolic dney, brain, etc.; and

complicates the controlling measures!

3.4 Role of HROS' antibodies (sIgA, IgA, IgG, etc. [13,31,36-43,53,54,54a]) in immune system

Although, this work, international conferences [14], we hope that it will have at least 1/4th weight to force the health sector obtain another angle

3.4.1 Innate immune system: mechanical barriers and inherited immune cells

Mechanical defense (cilia,

alveolar cells (alveolar {

, lymphocytes (in particular the T cells), etc., and their active molecules like cytokines: interferon, interleukins, etc cell defense mechanisms

Figure 10: General illustration of infections and innate immune systems (modified from [40,43])

3.4.2 Role of adapted immune system, in particular adapted antibody in general

Yes, our target for

within this sub-section:

Adapted antibodies (

illustrated figure 11).

Figure 11 (a,b) schematic expression of general immune processes (modified from [44])

7a: immunoglobulin with their

If there is infection by a pathogen or vaccine, the adopted immune system activated. Which means that during infection, the body

/indirectly initiate the T→B-plasma cell production's mechanisms [48-51], the body couldn't produce the desired adapted antibody on time and sufficiently!

3.4.3 HROS' immune system in general

Since, about the innate

The relation between HROS and adapted immunity (antibody) highlighted by many authors [10,35,36,41,55,56].

doubt whether mRNA effective against SARS-CoV-2! Anyway,

For HROS based

lumen-blood vessels during intact is dense, because of which antibodies due to their large size [47] and susceptible to

, the secretory IgA (SIgA) can act as an ever-changing environment [48] within tracts. Therefore, it is the main

3.4.4 Nature-Structure and function of SIgA

3.4.4.1 structure of SIgA

As seen below in figure 12,

and then with secretory components

Figure 12 (a,b,c,d) Structure of SIgA in different form, including stereochemistry based expression [37,50,61}

3.4.4.2 general-main function of SIgA

Anyhow, the main ,59,60-63}.

3.4.4.3 This antibody more studied with association of digestive system [23,37,42,45,48,49,59,63}. However, there are also tracts' mucosa.

3.4.4.4 Since our target is the SIgA's role in HROS, we have got works [20,21,37,40,43,45,46,48,52, surfaces.

3.4.4.5 The SIgA is created on the lamina propria environment [40,47-49,58,62,65}. Some authors [24,45,49,50,51,53,54, ,48,52} into the apical surface (mucus) of the epithelium to neutralize foreign bodies

3.4.5 What initiate SIgA's production and its formation mechanisms?

This is the core part for the given sub

3.4.5.1 What forms the SIgA?

The IgA is produced by

immunoglobulin A (IgA) antibodies

(pIgR). The receptor, a type

of the molecule, termed secretory component (SC), is released free or bound to IgA [42].

3.4.5.1 Schematized approach (in figural illustration) of showing the function of SIgA

Figure 13: schematically expression of how SIgA may be formed (modified from [44])

3.4.5.2 The SIgA main functions

Certainly, as others

and in clearance. Anyway, here under is illustration (figure 10), to visualize the SIgA's roles.

Figure 14 (a,b): Activation, Transcytosis, of [47,48,59,61])

3.4.5.3 Additional exploration on the induction-producing-functioning procedures of SIgA
Mucus starts intensively every day [71]; the Peyer's patches were the principal precursor source of IgA+ PCs. In addition, the naso pharynx-associated lymphoid tissues and the bronchus-associated lymphoid tissues (BALT immune inductive sites [48]).

For better visualization, where about the SIgA formation within the lamina propria

3.4.6 SIgA characteristics and literature (partially) in table form are shown

Although, we tried to forward main issues about SIgA in 3.4.5 in text and figure based form, due to its decisive theme of the

3.4.6.1 what induces the SIgA's production; what type of cell produces it and where?

Of course, there may not be necessary metabolites – metabolites, which should come from digestive system into the blood stream.

Therefore, alone the argument of many authors (refer to table 2) that the SIgA is produced within the lamina propria of basal side of epithelia [40] couldn't be enough to conclude that B-plasma cells of serum origin do not participating in SIgA production!

Table 2: Sample of references, authors which suggests the source of SIgA

reference	Type of the study		What trigger the production	By which cells	Where is producing
	Case-experm	review			
45			Nasal infect DC, etc	, IgA+→IgA-	Nasal l
47		✓	Ho ontrol	Local f lamina	Lamina pral cells
48	✓	✓	DC- inte lamina	Local placell	Payer's patch
49			Bronc ens		Dimeric lamina prop
51		✓	Macr , Epith	Matu cells	Lung:
53	✓		SARS-2	MALT	tissue
58	✓		: epithet, DC	Mucoplasma cells	crophages,
59		✓		Mucosal meane	Peyer's LF

Yes, if the issue is about intestinal SIgA, we can agree that plasma cells of the Peyer's Patches may be the source of IgA. To the contrary, result, additional to the above (from dozens) that assure us about the local production of SIgA in response to only local infection. Whereas, the last 2 (about the possibility of IMAV's involvement in the production of SIgA

3.4.6.2 Do IMAVs induce the production of SIgA?

Within the above points (3

collected a direct experimental-case studies with some additional literature (in which enclosed references of experimental-case

Table 3: comparative literature that are focusing on where and how SIgA produces

Reference	Study type		result	Recommendation
	clinical	review		
37	✓		Nasal production	Local vaccination
44	✓		COVID-19 mucosal immunity	Local antibody
46	✓		IMAV elicit IgG, but nasal v the SIgA	Local vaccination
53		✓	SIgA induced in virus infection	nation

55			Intranasa is better for and new strains	better
62	✓	✓	Plant SIgA production SIgA for local vaccine	l
66	✓		intranasal vaccine	al vanation
67	✓	✓	Protecting from hRCV by IMAV	Lvaccination
68	✓		t effective	Lovaction
69			Serum TB is useless	
Here under are the only two authors (at least indirectly) that confirm about the effectiveness of IMAV				
21			A journalist told that scientists confirm IMAV's efficacy	IMAV
70	✓		IMAV is effective for seropositive patients	can Seropositive?

In the table 3, as a sample we have inserted only half among more than 20 literature that directly/indirectly confirmed the works [21] as of [53] wrote (before having IMAV shots)'.

3.4.6.3 How far the data of experimental – clinical case studies mentioned in table 3 satisfied us?

Certainly, the researchers design in works, where inclined to local vaccination, and more those of the two [21,70] which tried to show us as if the IMAV can induce 3X3 clearly identified experimental variables: control-infected-vaccinated among at least 3 types of ages and 3 geographical (

... an epidemiology-clinical based survey (antibody count): 3 variables:- control (neither infected nor vaccinated); infected (but not vaccinated) and vaccinated (but not infected). With 3 types of variables by ages: 7-12; 35-40; and 65-70 years. If possible

Figure 15: a screen shot of a part of methodology from article [6])

However, even control (not IMAVs for production of this main mucosal antibody – the SIgA! Nevertheless, both the anti and pro IMAV works enclosed in on time and sufficient manner within HROS”.

3.4.6.4 Re-expand on the IgA-HROS issues

HROS tracts couldn't be regulated than systemic IgG and IgA Abs [44] and they are poorly induced by conventional injected vaccines.” However, this antibody is neither in intact nor after IMAV (unless, the vaccine damages the epithelium) can and the HROS tract) infected by a pathogen. Moreover, there may not necessary to trigger or train the body to produce the SIgA study decreases the level of our beliefs on facemask [4] efficacy if we are using it for a long time. Because, what we realized in roducing SIgA.

3.4.7 Exclusive summary-based discussion for - why IMAV doesn't induce the SIgA's production?

3.4.7.1 What is IMAVs' common role?

It is a fact that IMAVs in (via CD4 T cells) trigger the B plasma cell to produce the desired antibodies. IMAV was

and sufficient manner) protection if they are brought to the place where the pathogen/antigen is acting. On the other hand

3.4.7.2 Humoral Antibody vs. HROS's pathogens

Most (if not all)

the production of the humoral based adapted antibodies, and even if such antibodies have already been produced, they may not approach the HROS pathogen/antigen before it destroyed the tract! This leads us to a provocative question: What then does protect the HROS from being infected?

3.4.7.3 HROS's immune system

The luminal surfaces of the body tracts, such as: the gastrointestinal and urinary tracts; as well as the mucosal-

dense covering of the tract, primarily by mucosal and epithelial cells. In addition, there is another powerful innate der. Additionally,

3.4.7.4 Hiding blood vessels

The circulatory vessels, especially not to have a direct contact with the luminal surface, the blood vessels are

that humoral antibodies will interfere with mucosal-epithelial surface-based pathogens/antigens. Furthermore, since the HROS

signal to stimulate B plasma cells. Even if this were to happen, it would be after the HROS barrier system had been

HROS tracts?

3.4.7.5 HROS's adapted antibody is - SIgA

Well, if the mechanical

intensive study, we found that the antibody SIgA serves as the main antibody (if not the only one) that not only protects

y tract.

What is SIgA? It is a

that is not produced by B plasma cells in the bloodstream, but rather is produced

, unless the epithelium

nor activates its polymeric IgA receptor to transcytose the SIgA into the lumen surface. To make all clear, let us pass once

– how and where the SIgA forms?

3.4.7.6 Where and how SIgA forms

The main

propria; the binding process of dIgA with the secretory component of epithelial cells also within the lamina propria;

. All of these 5 conditions (processes) also clearly indicate to us that this antibody is produced at least within the

all these theoretical data we can synthesize that the formation of SIgA does not occur at least within the humoral system.

3.4.7.7 Role of IMAV in SIgA production

However, according

.6) give us the right to postulate - IMAV does not train the body to produce SIgA. Furthermore, induction of SIgA

invaders appear

and mainly Peyer's patches. Additionally, all of these are located within the lamina propria's environment, but not

. In particular, we have no solid
of IgA→dIgA is not in the B memory cell. Therefore,

3.4.7.8 Experimental-clinical case studies

Due to our

-clinical case studies, which were available (freely accessible) from Internet sources. Although we are not completely satisfied as saliva samples, but not within the circulatory system. Furthermore, in their works, the production of SIgA does have been infected prior to vaccination. Thus the sum of these facts incline us to the postulation – IMAV do not participate

3.4.7.9 Questions and answers that lead us to general conclusions:

If irritation of the

”. However, local vaccination can only contribute to SIgA in the upper HROS tract (see sub articles 3.1 and 3.2 or we it a simple and practical measure - staying away from places where the pathogen might be present or wearing a face mask answers for the above, can't we eradicate pathogens, if not for a century, then at least for several decades?

3.4.7.10 Conclusion

IMAVs train our body

systemic pathogens/antigens. Since HROS is nearly avascular, system-based antibodies therefore cannot reach the pathogen/

3.4.8 Recommendation

Although, since this work has only the fourth weight from our six groups of scientific justifications, we can intramuscular/subcutaneous vaccination. However, preventing pathogens from entering the nostrils and oral

Let this work memorize my sister Mintwab Temesgen and 7 million others victims of this fault pandemic

4 General conclusion-recommendations derived from the main article (with the six groups of justifications

4.2 Keen recommendations:

4.2.1 Governmental bodies shouldn't use such disaster for their political benefit. Instead, they must form a responsible body for each type of infectious disease. Surely, three years ago, as shown in our works [2,4}, the committee's members must be only with relevant specialization-experiences; and no authority should interfere against the Committee's professional decisions.

4.2.2 World organizations such as the WHO and its leader, the UN, must independently monitor, assess, and control infections without unprofessional interference from politicians and business-oriented institutions

4.2.3 The Nobel Prize Committee should engage in evaluating the quality of any reasonable research and its outcome.” Not only to fulfill Alfred Nobel's WILL, but also to increase the influence of the Nobel Prize Committee by periodically giving relevant laureates better tasked with assessing current science-based issues, resolve related disputes or make suggestions of their own. Therefore,

4.2.4 To this respected neutral institution. We kindly suggest: let the Nobel Prize Committee, with its prestigious recognitions, form an investigator task force, members of which are relevant Nobel Prize winners (physiologists, immunologists, biochemists) to evaluate all research results related to this pandemic. For our part, we are too eager to share our 20 years back understandings on Corona and 7 works on COVID-19 issues, as well as the recent research conclusion that “not only against SARS-CoV-2, but also an intramuscularly administrable mode of vaccine is not feasible to stop others respiratory tracts based pathogens too”. By performing such monitoring, The Nobel Committee may decrease messes in research’s sphere. Unless,

4.2.5 The world will have no guarantee that deliberately/innocently another disaster will not be repeated.

6. List of used and cited references

[1] Dessalegn Temesgen Leye / Disclosing Faults; correcting them; and revealing others Vital, but yet unnoticed Preventable Prophylactic Measures that must be implemented in battling against Covid-19’s Pandemic (IJISRR September 2020)

[51] Francesca Polverino, Leen J. M. Seys, Ken R. Bracke, and Caroline A. Owen / B cells in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: moving to center stage: B Cell Development in Health

[52] José A. Bengoechea / Secretary IgA and COPD: A New Kid on the Block? / American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine/Volume 184, Issue 3/ <https://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.201105-0821ED>/PubMed: 21804117

[53] Kaori Sano, Disha Bhavsar, Gagandeep Singh, et al. / SARS-CoV-2 vaccination induces mucosal antibody responses in previously infected individuals / J. Nature Communication / <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-32389-8>

[54] CECIL CZERKINSKY, SHIRLEY J. PRINCE, SUZANNE M. MICHALEK, et. al. / IgA antibody-producing cells in peripheral blood after antigen ingestion: Evidence for a common mucosal immune system in humans / Proc. Nati. Acad. Sci. USA / Immunology/Vol. 84, pp. 2449-2453, April 1987

[54a] Scott McComb, Aude Thiriot, Bassel Akache, Lakshmi Krishnan Introduction to the Immune System / Doi: 10.1007/978-1-4939-9597-4 | <https://www.researchgate.net>

[55] Sam Afkhami,1,5 Michael R. D’Agostino,2,5 Ali Zhang,2 Hannah D. Stacey, et al. / Respiratory mucosal delivery of next-generation COVID-19 vaccine provides robust protection against both ancestral and variant strains of SARS-CoV-2 / j. Cell 185, 896–915, March 3, 2022 897

[71] Yue Li, Liang Jin, and Tongxin Chen / Interplay between Immune Cells and their Microenvironment Niches: The Effects of Secretary IgA in the Mucosal Immune System / Volume 2020 | Article ID 2032057 | <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/2032057>